

The Significance of the Belt and Road Initiative in Sudan–China Relations: Opportunities and Challenge

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ABSTRACT

The article investigates the importance of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) (formerly the One Belt One Road (OBOR) initiative) to the relations between Sudan and China, with a focus on opportunities, challenges, and infrastructure cooperation. It examines the core aspects of bilateral ties between Sudan and China, the level of BRI implementation in Sudan, and the potential impact of BRI on Sudan's economic and infrastructure development.

This study uses a qualitative descriptive approach and secondary data sources, including academic literature, policy documents, official reports, and institutional documents. Furthermore, the SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analytical framework is used to analyze Sudan's engagement in the BRI and the institutional, political, and economic conditions affecting the implementation of BRI projects in Sudan.

The results reveal that throughout its history, infrastructure investment, energy agreements, and economic cooperation have contributed to Sudan-China relations. The report highlights opportunities for deepening cooperation between Sudan and China in infrastructure and transport, particularly in the railway sector, given Sudan's strategic position along the Red Sea and its infrastructure needs. Yet several challenges remain in implementing BRI-related projects in Sudan, including political instability, lack of institutional coordination, financial constraints, security concerns, and governance restrictions.

The research conducted for the Port Sudan-Adré railway project reveals the absence of integrated institutional procedures and financial mechanisms to facilitate its realization, even after the project has passed the feasibility stage and received political support.

The article's conclusion argues that institutional coordination should be reinforced, governance and policy harmonization strengthened, investment and funding mechanisms improved, and infrastructure planning coordinated with Sudan's long-term development agenda to enable Sudan to benefit from the BRI. The report recommends supporting intergovernmental coordination mechanisms, developing regulations, and building strong ties with international and regional financial partners to support sustainable infrastructure development and regional economic integration.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Introduction The relationship between China and Sudan has been solid, close, and stable since 1958, when China opened its diplomatic office in Sudan. Regardless of changes in the government, relations have not been affected, and their collaboration has been maintained. Barber (2020) asserts that “before 2011, China's bilateral ties with Sudan were among its best in Africa, with economic interest being one of the key factors in this relationship.”

This cooperation peaked during the days of oil production and achieved good economic stability, attracted foreign direct investments, and gave rise to a strong currency rate of the Sudanese pound against the dollar. But this stability was short-lived, as economic decline began after Sudan lost two-thirds of its oil revenue, which went to the Republic of South Sudan after its independence from Sudan in 2011. Since this division, Sudan's oil imports to China

dropped nearly 80% in 2011-2012 and continued to decline year by year (Barber, 2020).

With this in mind, this study seeks to identify new opportunities for cooperation between the two countries within the Belt and Road Initiative. The Belt and Road Center 2024 indicates that China has signed 200 cooperation documents with 150 countries and 32 international organizations under the Belt and Road Initiative (Belt and Road Center 2024). In infrastructure construction, cooperation between China and Belt and Road countries has been successful in ports, railways, highways, power plants, aviation, and telecommunications. I have tried to highlight the importance of OBOR for improving relations between the two countries, as well as the challenges both countries face in implementing the OBOR strategy in Sudan.

The article first briefly outlines the nature of OBOR, then examines the fundamental pillars of Sudan-China ties, and discusses the pros and challenges of OBOR implementation in Sudan. So, I think those of you who read this essay will do their share to produce a good research paper on this subject.

2. BACKGROUND

In 2013, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) – or One Belt One Road (OBOR) Initiative – was officially launched as a global development and connectivity initiative to help build economic cooperation, trade integration, and infrastructure connectivity in Asia, Africa, Europe, and parts of Latin America. A combination of large-scale investments in transport networks, energy infrastructure, logistics corridors, ports, and industrial cooperation zones to develop transnational connectivity and economic integration is a key element of the strategy (Rolland, 2017; Yu, 2017).

Since its inception, the BRI has emerged as a key element of China’s foreign economic strategy and a crucial tool for shaping China’s interactions with developing countries. Economically and geopolitically, scholars have suggested that the BRI has two aspects. The initiative forms part of China’s wider plans to transform the region and world through “the Belt and Road Initiative” (BRI) and “development of the regional infrastructure network” (RIB) (Callahan, 2016). Along the same lines, proponents in the camp of Jones and Zeng (2019) argue that the BRI should not be viewed solely as an infrastructure project, but as a concept linked to China’s political and strategic goals. Concurrently, it is suggested that the BRI projects facilitate the infrastructure development, economic growth, and regional integration of the countries involved, particularly in the infrastructure-starved developing countries of South Asia and Southeast Asia (Summers, 2016).

As the BRI was launched, the critical sea lanes, expanding markets, and infrastructure needs of Africa have increasingly made it an integral component of the BRI. Chinese engagement in Africa is mostly through transport

infrastructure, ports, railway, and energy and telecommunication (ZiroMwatela & Changfeng 2016). Chinese-funded infrastructure projects have had a major impact on changing regional transport and commercial networks – particularly in East Africa. Mboya (2023) contends that the BRI has helped reshape regional economic ties in East Africa by investing in infrastructure for connectivity and logistics corridors.

In this respect, Sudan enjoys a strategic geographic position, being situated along the Red Sea corridor, which connects Africa, the Middle East, and Asia. Sudan has a port on the Red Sea, Port Sudan, which is an important marine gateway that might boost regional commerce and connectivity projects associated with the BRI. Sudan also has several landlocked neighbors, such as Chad and South Sudan, which could further raise the country’s potential importance as a regional transport and transit hub. Economic cooperation, political engagement, and infrastructural investment are features of Sudan-China relations. Bilateral cooperation has significantly increased since the Chinese became actively involved in Sudan’s oil industry in the 1990s. Sudan’s oil industry development was led by Chinese state-owned companies, particularly the China National Petroleum Corporation (CNPC), in oil exploration, pipelines, refineries, and export facilities (Large, 2014). As scholars have noted, China’s involvement in Sudan gradually expanded from energy to infrastructure investments, including roads, dams, bridges, and power stations, and it is China’s largest economic partner in Sudan at this point (Patey, 2014; Barber, 2020). But during the last decade, there have been tremendous changes in Sudan’s economic and political climate. The secession of South Sudan in 2011 further compounded Sudan’s economic instability and fiscal pressures, as it lost a significant share of its oil revenue.

Moreover, the country’s potential to attract investment and to properly execute large-scale infrastructure projects has been hampered by frequent political instability, institutional weaknesses, previous international sanctions, and the current armed conflict. These situations offer opportunities and challenges for Sudan to play a role in the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). On the other hand, the BRI offers opportunities for infrastructure development, regional connectivity, trade expansion, and investment collaborations. However, a number of developing countries participating in the program continue to have concerns about debt sustainability and governance capacity, as well as institutional coordination and political instability issues in implementing infrastructure projects (Hurley et al. 2018; Brautigam, 2020).

Recent research also suggests that participation in the BRI can boost infrastructure growth and development, but the implications for long-term development are highly dependent on institutional capacity and the quality of domestic governance. Lu et al. (2021) noted that while

participation in the BRI could lead to increased overall economic growth, it has differential effects on inclusive and sustainable development outcomes across participating countries.

This finding is especially relevant to the Sudan case, where institutional fragmentation and financial constraints continue to affect the design and implementation of infrastructure. Sudan should be evaluated prudently for its development opportunities and political, institutional, and financial issues in relation to its involvement in the Belt and Road Initiative. Knowledge of these dynamics is crucial to grasp the potential of Sudan–China collaboration within the framework of BRI, particularly in the context of critical infrastructure projects such as the Port Sudan–Adré railway project.

3. METHODOLOGY

Based on a qualitative descriptive research design, this study aims to examine the importance and impact of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) on the Sudan–China relationship across three areas: infrastructure cooperation, institutional coordination, and implementation challenges. A qualitative approach is suitable because it involves interpreting political, economic, and institutional relationships rather than quantitative relationships.

Secondary data sources are mainly used in research; these include peer-reviewed journal articles, books, policy reports, government official documents, institutional correspondence, conference reports, and publications from international organizations. These sources were employed to explore the evolution of Sudan–China relationships, the implementation of BRI in infrastructure development, and the challenges of implementing large-scale infrastructure projects in Sudan.

To enhance the analytical structure, the study has used a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) Analysis to evaluate Sudan's involvement in the BRI. This structure was chosen for its ability to assess internal and external factors, including institutional capacity and political stability, financing opportunities, and regional geopolitical environments.

The study also explores the concrete possibilities and limitations for BRI-related infrastructure cooperation in Sudan through taking the Port Sudan–Adré railway project as a case study. It was chosen because it holds strategic importance for regional connectivity and is relevant to transport infrastructure and economic integration issues in East and Central Africa. The analysis looks at financing, governance, institutional coordination, and implementation processes issues.

Moreover, qualitative content analysis was used to identify themes and patterns within the collected data. The study, however, has drawbacks, including reliance on secondary sources and the lack of up-to-date official

information due to political unrest and the current conflict in Sudan. This analysis is largely based on policy frameworks, institutional processes, and planning dynamics, as the railway project has not been implemented.

4. OVERVIEW OF ONE BELT ONE ROAD INITIATIVE

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), formerly referred to as the One Belt One Road (OBOR) Initiative, was formally launched in 2013 as a global plan for development and connectivity in the region of Asia, Africa, Europe, and other regions to boost economic cooperation, integration, and infrastructure development. The project is a land-sea trade corridor that aims to enhance transport connectivity via investments in transport infrastructure, ports, railways, energy infrastructure, and logistics systems (Yu, 2017; Rolland, 2017).

BRI is divided into two parts: the Silk Road Economic Belt and the 21st Century Maritime Silk Road. The land-based Silk Road Economic Belt aims to improve land-based transport and energy links between China, Central Asia, the Middle East, and Europe. The Maritime Silk Road emphasizes the maritime connectivity between China and Southeast Asia, Africa, and Europe via strategic ports and shipping infrastructure (Liu & Dunford, 2016).

The purpose of these connectivity networks is to encourage regional economic integration, investment, and trade expansion. The BRI has been subjected to a variety of interpretations by scholars. Others see the scheme largely as an economic development initiative that would help fill infrastructure gaps and encourage international economic collaboration, especially in developing nations that lack the capacity for infrastructure (Summers, 2016). Others have noted that the BRI is also part of China's broader geopolitical and strategic agenda, reflecting its growing influence and role in global economic governance (Callahan, 2016; Jones & Zeng, 2019).

The varying interpretations show that the BRI is an economic and political project with intricate global consequences. The strategic trade routes, the infrastructure demand, and China's growing economic ties with Africa have made Africa an important region within the BRI framework. The Chinese presence in African infrastructure has expanded across transportation, ports and railways, telecommunications, and energy development (Sun, 2018).

Infrastructure connectivity is one of the core areas of BRI cooperation in Africa and could support regional integration and trade facilitation, provided that robust institutional coordination and a sustainable funding system are in place. Simultaneously, the BRI has sparked considerable debate over the sustainability of debt, transparency, environmental impacts, and governance issues. Lisinge (2020) notes that, in some participating countries, there are financial and governance risks due to poor

institutional capacity and financing arrangements for large-scale infrastructure projects.

Likewise, Hurley et al. (2018) remind us that the assessment of Chinese overseas financing should not be based on the “civilisationalist view,” but should also take into account the domestic political and institutional environments of recipient countries. In recent years, the BRI has continued to evolve in response to global economic developments and criticism of large infrastructure loans.

Some studies indicate that China has increasingly focused on smaller, more focused projects, as well as sustainability, regional partnerships, and risk management (Brautigam, 2020). Overall, the BRI is a significant tool for understanding current China–Africa relations and infrastructure cooperation. The initiative opens up opportunities for infrastructure development, strengthening governance capacity, financing sustainability, and addressing institutional coordination challenges for countries like Sudan.

5. THE MAIN RELATIONSHIP PILLARS OF CHINA AND SUDAN

5.1 Historical Development of Sudan–China Relations

Relations between Sudan and China have deep historical roots that extend back centuries through trade and cultural exchange along the ancient Maritime Silk Road. According to Mukhtar (2018), maritime connections between the eastern ports of Sudan and the Far East existed as early as the Western Han Dynasty. Similarly, Ahmed (2015) notes that archaeological discoveries, including Chinese pottery remains found in eastern Sudan and the ancient city of Meroe, indicate historical interactions between Sudan and China dating back to at least the Tang Dynasty. Historical evidence from Arabic and Chinese sources further suggests that the Red Sea ports of Sudan and Ethiopia maintained commercial links with China between the first and sixteenth centuries AD.

Modern diplomatic relations between Sudan and China developed significantly after Sudan recognized the People’s Republic of China in 1959. Bilateral cooperation expanded considerably during the 1990s when Sudan faced severe economic difficulties and international sanctions. Following the imposition of United States sanctions on Sudan in 1997, Chinese companies became major investors in Sudan’s oil sector. According to Hui (2015), Chinese investment contributed substantially to the development of Sudan’s petroleum industry through investments in oil exploration, refineries, pipelines, and transportation infrastructure. This cooperation enabled Sudan to partially mitigate the economic impact of sanctions while supporting China’s growing energy demands.

Economic cooperation between the two countries gradually expanded beyond the oil sector to include infrastructure development and public services. Chinese-supported projects in Sudan included roads, bridges, dams,

electricity infrastructure, and public facilities such as the Friendship Hall and Friendship Hospital in Omdurman (China-embassy in Sudan website, 2020). Briceno-Garmendia (2011) further observed that China became one of the largest financiers of infrastructure projects in Sudan, supporting investments in power generation, roads, and dam construction, including the Merowe Dam project and related transmission infrastructure.

Several studies have highlighted the strategic nature of Sudan–China relations. Sidlo (2020) noted that Sudan was among the largest recipients of Chinese financing in the Middle East and North Africa region between 2000 and 2014. Hui (2015) also argues that cooperation between the two countries continued even after the separation of South Sudan in 2011, reflecting the resilience of bilateral relations despite political and economic transformations.

More recently, Sudan’s post-conflict reconstruction needs and infrastructure challenges have renewed interest in cooperation under the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). Chen and Han (2019) argue that Chinese-supported infrastructure cooperation can contribute to economic recovery and reconstruction in conflict-affected states. In the Sudanese context, the destruction caused by the conflict that began in April 2023 has increased the importance of infrastructure rehabilitation and regional connectivity initiatives.

5.2 Partnership Agreements and Strategic Cooperation

Cooperation between Sudan and China has been institutionalized through several strategic agreements and sectoral partnerships covering infrastructure, agriculture, energy, health, and development cooperation. In 2015, the two countries signed a strategic partnership agreement aimed at strengthening cooperation across multiple sectors, including oil, agriculture, mining, and industrial development (Sudantribune Website, 2015). The agreement reflected growing political and economic ties between the two countries and emphasized long-term cooperation based on mutual interests and economic development.

Subsequent agreements expanded cooperation into additional sectors. In 2018, discussions between Sudanese President Omar Al-Bashir and Chinese President Xi Jinping emphasized strengthening bilateral cooperation in energy, agriculture, mining, and infrastructure development. Sudan also sought Chinese support for debt restructuring and increased investment cooperation during this period.

Cooperation later extended into healthcare, agriculture, and water infrastructure projects. In 2020, Sudan and China strengthened cooperation in the health sector through agreements involving the Sudanese Ministry of Health and the Chinese Embassy in Sudan (almashhadalsudani Website, n.d.). Additional agreements included Chinese support for livestock and agricultural development projects, groundwater well construction

projects, and agricultural technology cooperation initiatives (Sudanese Ministry of investment, 2023).

Chinese officials and Sudanese leaders have repeatedly emphasized the importance of Sudan within the Belt and Road Initiative framework due to its strategic geographic location along the Red Sea corridor. Statements by Chinese and Sudanese officials highlighted cooperation in transport infrastructure, agriculture, ports, and regional connectivity as important areas for future collaboration (Website of the Chinese Embassy in Sudan, 2023).

Despite the broad scope of bilateral agreements, implementation challenges remain significant. Several agreed projects have experienced delays or remain incomplete due to financing constraints, administrative obstacles, and political instability (Ministry of Finance, 2023). In addition, the conflict that erupted in Sudan in April 2023 has further disrupted infrastructure projects and weakened Sudan’s ability to secure new financing arrangements. These challenges highlight the importance of institutional coordination, financial sustainability, and political stability in ensuring the successful implementation of Sudan–China cooperation projects.

6. THE IMPLEMENTATION OF ONE BELT ONE ROAD INITIATIVE IN SUDAN

China’s Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) have the potential to contribute to infrastructure development and economic recovery in Sudan through expanded cooperation in transportation, energy, and regional connectivity projects. Some scholars argue that Chinese-supported infrastructure investment may support post-conflict reconstruction and economic stabilization in developing countries affected by political instability and weak infrastructure systems (Chen & Han, 2019). In the Sudanese context, infrastructure investment has become increasingly important following the economic challenges associated with political instability, economic decline, and the armed conflict that erupted in April 2023.

6.1 Implementation of the Port Sudan–Adré Project in the Context of the Belt and Road Initiative

The Port Sudan–Adré railway project, sometimes referred to as the Port Sudan–N’Djamena railway project, represents one of the most significant proposed regional transport projects linked to Sudan’s engagement with the Belt and Road Initiative. The project aims to connect Port Sudan on the Red Sea with western Sudan and neighboring landlocked countries, particularly Chad, with the broader objective of improving regional trade connectivity and transportation infrastructure.

Sudan officially joined the Belt and Road Initiative in August 2017 through a cooperation document signed between Sudan and China. The agreement established a framework for future cooperation projects but required separate agreements and financing arrangements for

individual projects. However, available documents indicate that no final implementation agreement was concluded for the Port Sudan–Adré railway project despite political discussions surrounding its inclusion within BRI-related cooperation initiatives.

Official correspondence between Sudanese institutions indicates that Sudan repeatedly requested Chinese support for the railway project between 2018 and 2019. Project documents reveal that Sudan proposed the project during China–Africa cooperation meetings and requested its inclusion among projects associated with the Belt and Road Initiative. A feasibility study for the project was reportedly prepared by a consortium of Chinese companies, and discussions were held between the Sudanese Railway Corporation and China Railway 16th Bureau Group Co., Ltd. regarding possible implementation arrangements.

The project possesses several characteristics consistent with the objectives of the Belt and Road Initiative, particularly in relation to regional connectivity, trade facilitation, and infrastructure integration between coastal and landlocked regions. Similar transport infrastructure projects supported by China have been implemented in several African countries, including Ethiopia and Kenya. Nevertheless, despite political support from both Sudanese and Chinese stakeholders, the project has not progressed to the implementation stage.

The available evidence suggests that financing constraints and weak institutional coordination have been major obstacles to project implementation. Correspondence between Sudanese institutions demonstrates limited coordination among the Ministry of Transport, the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and the Sudanese Railway Corporation regarding financing mechanisms and implementation responsibilities. This situation reflects broader governance and institutional coordination challenges affecting infrastructure planning in Sudan.

6.2 The Current Status of the Implementation of the Belt and Road Initiative and Its Challenges

Since it was first proposed in 2015 through a memorandum signed by the Sudanese and Chadian presidents to the Chinese president, the Port Sudan–Adri railway project has received regional attention as an alternative economic corridor and a catalyst for regional integration. However, its practical implementation still faces some institutional and financial challenges.

Official documents indicate that the Sudanese government has taken necessary technical steps, such as preparing a feasibility study through specialized Chinese companies and signing a memorandum of understanding with the Chinese company CCRC-16 during the 2018 China–Africa Summit in Beijing. A vision was also reached to implement the project’s first phase from Port Sudan to Sennar, at an estimated cost of 2.3 billion euros. However, the final agreement has yet to be signed due to the lack of consensus

between government agencies on the funding mechanism and the lack of clarity of institutional coordination among the Ministry of Finance, the Railway Authority, and the Ministry of Investment. This reflects a structural weakness in institutional coordination and governance within the administrative system, which has been confirmed by the literature in its evaluation of infrastructure projects in developing countries such as Sudan (El-Beily, 2015).

Relying on external funding without a clear national funding plan or a harmonized legal framework adds to the project's fragility. Despite the existence of the PPP law since 2021, its actual implementation in railway projects faces institutional and legislative bureaucracy, and there is no unified executive body for transport projects, which makes coordination difficult and prolongs decision-making.

One of the main challenges lies in the funding mechanism. Although there is an initial commitment from Chinese companies to implement the project based on the feasibility study, the Sudanese side has not received official confirmation from the Chinese government that the project will be included in the Belt and Road Initiative funding. This is due to several reasons, most notably the weak capacity of Sudanese institutions to attract loans, the low credit rating, and the absence of sovereign guarantees. In this context, the Sudanese side is reluctant to sign the agreement without a clear funding commitment, especially in light of the financial pressures the country is facing and the sharp decline in foreign exchange reserves.

In addition, Sudan lacks clear strategies to attract financing through Belt and Road tools such as Chinese Exim Bank loans or the BOT model, similar to projects implemented by China in Ethiopia, Kenya, and Nigeria, although Sudan is a shareholder in the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB) (Ministry of Finance, 2023).

Since the outbreak of war in Sudan in April 2023, challenges to project implementation have increased. Key state institutions, including the Ministry of Finance and the Ministry of Transport, have been affected, the work of executive bodies in charge of infrastructure has been disrupted, and opportunities for dialogue with international investors have diminished. Moreover, the war has negatively affected Sudan's political credibility and raised the level of sovereign risk, prompting most international partners to freeze their transactions until the situation stabilizes. It is therefore necessary to reassess the project's priorities at the current stage, strengthen the legislative and governance framework, and develop a recovery plan that includes the involvement of regional institutions (such as the African Development Bank) and new private sector partners.

The Port Sudan-Adri project is still on paper despite completing technical studies. Lack of institutional coordination, a weak financing framework, and the repercussions of the war are the main obstacles to the implementation of the project. For the project to see the light

of day, serious institutional reforms are needed, and international confidence in Sudan's ability to implement major projects with sustainable partnerships must be restored.

7. ANALYSIS OF SUDAN'S PARTICIPATION IN BRI:

This study uses the SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis approach to assess Sudan's involvement in the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). The framework serves to evaluate the internal and external factors to be considered for Sudan to take advantage of BRI-related cooperation and infrastructure development projects.

7.1 Strengths:

Sudan has a few strategic advantages that could enhance its capacity to engage in the Belt and Road Initiative. First, Sudan and China have longstanding political and economic ties nurtured by successive administrations. Historical ties have helped foster ongoing bilateral cooperation in areas such as energy, infrastructure, and trade.

Second, Sudan is strategically located on the Red Sea trade route and thus plays a pivotal role as a potential gateway between Africa, the Middle East, and Asia. Sudan's ports are also on the maritime trade route, and they are near several landlocked countries in Africa, making it a vital node in the region's transport and logistics networks.

Thirdly, Sudan has ample natural resources, including agricultural land, water resources, livestock, oil, and gold. These resources also provide opportunities for economic cooperation and investment in the framework of the BRI.

Furthermore, Sudan and China have established several institutional arrangements for cooperation, including the 2015 strategic partnership agreement and joint ministerial and technical committees. These institutional arrangements could offer an important basis for future cooperation and policy coordination.

7.2 Weaknesses:

Although Sudan has these benefits, the country faces significant problems of its own that hinder its effective use of the BRI. The country experienced political turmoil and frequent government changes, which have hindered policy stability and investor confidence. The country has been experiencing political instability and frequent changes of government, leading to a lack of policy continuity and investor confidence.

Moreover, economic problems, such as high external debt, high inflation, and reliance on external financing, limit Sudan's ability to finance large-scale infrastructure projects. Poverty of institutions is also a significant constraint. Infrastructure planning and project implementation are made difficult by overlapping institutional responsibilities, administrative inefficiencies, and poor coordination among government agencies. The

study of the Port Sudan–Adré rail project shows that the lack of coordination among relevant institutions led to delays in financing and implementation.

7.3 Opportunities:

The Belt and Road Initiative offers Sudan a number of opportunities in economic development and regional integration. BRI investments may help to enhance transport infrastructure, energy systems, logistics networks, and regional trade connectivity. Railway and maritime transport play a special role given Sudan's geographical location and its potential as a regional transit route for landlocked countries. The program can also open the door to greater foreign direct investment and financing for infrastructure development.

Furthermore, there may be scope for reengaging in economic cooperation and investment between Sudan and China, given Sudan's prior debt restructuring and its financial cooperation with China. In addition, regional connectivity projects, such as railway corridors and port development, may bolster cross-border trade and contribute to overall regional economic integration in East and Central Africa.

7.4 Threats:

There are several external and structural challenges that hinder Sudan's ability to take advantage of the Belt and Road Initiative. Political insecurity and armed conflict remain among the main obstacles to infrastructure investment and long-term development planning. Sudan's conflict, which started in April 2023, has further undermined institutional capacity and investor confidence. Financial instability and high debt burden also pose risks to infrastructure financing and debt sustainability.

Furthermore, geopolitical issues and security concerns in the region could impact the execution of regional connectivity initiatives. An additional challenge is to address implementation gaps. Sudan and China have signed several cooperation agreements, but the implementation of many projects is delayed, incomplete, or not underway. This raises issues of institutional preparedness, funding models, and project governance capacity.

7.5 Challenges & Opportunities Based on SWOT Analysis:

Overall, the SWOT analysis indicates opportunities and structural challenges for Sudan's participation in the Belt and Road Initiative. Sudan has significant geographical and economic potential, but this is constrained by political instability, poor institutional coordination, and limited financial resources.

The results indicate that better governance practices, coordination among state institutions, and improved infrastructure planning are important for successful participation in the BRI. Strategic infrastructure projects are particularly poorly coordinated at the institutional level, thereby lowering Sudan's capacity to finance and successfully

implement large projects.

The analysis further underscores the need to implement sustainable financing approaches to reduce over-reliance on external financing. Fostering P3 mechanisms and strengthening the legal and regulatory frameworks for infrastructure investment might help build investor confidence and implementation capacity.

In conclusion, Sudan's strategic location and infrastructure requirements offer excellent opportunities for cooperation within the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative. Yet, the opportunities to exploit these are heavily dependent on political stability, institutional coordination, enhanced governance capacity, and sustainable financing and implementation methods for infrastructure projects.

8. CONCLUSION

The present paper examines the significance of BRI for Sudan–China relations, particularly through the lens of infrastructure cooperation, institutional coordination, and the challenges of implementing major strategic projects such as the Port Sudan–Adré. This study used a qualitative descriptive design with a SWOT analytical framework to explore the political, economic, institutional, and strategic context of Sudan for participation in BRI.

Results show that the relationship between Sudan and China has developed over a long history of political and economic cooperation, and it has significantly increased in the 1990s, when the two countries ramped up cooperation in oil and infrastructure. China has been responsible for financing the expansion of Sudan's energy, transport, public services, and key development projects. The bilateral cooperation expanded from energy-related to a more strategic convergence in areas such as industry development, agriculture, health care delivery, transport, and regional connectivity. Sudan, with its strategic position along the corridor linking East and Central Africa to the Red Sea, has great potential to become a future transport and logistics hub within the Belt and Road Initiative.

The implementation of BRI infrastructure cooperation helps recover from economic losses, integrate regional trade, and rehabilitate the most affected industries: railways, ports, and transportation. For instance, the Port Sudan–Adré railway project symbolizes the importance of regional connectivity initiatives, which can enhance trade access for landlocked neighboring countries and strengthen Sudan's strategic position as a regional economic hub.

Yet this study also reveals that Sudan faced numerous political and economic challenges and institutional bottlenecks that hindered its ability to fully harness the BRI's potential. Political unrest, weak governance, lack of inter-institutional cooperation, limited funding availability, and administrative inefficiencies are obstacles to the functioning of large-scale infrastructure projects.

Inadequate financing mechanisms for sustainability

and decentralized institutional frameworks are stifling project implementation, even in the wake of political support, feasibility studies, and ongoing diplomatic efforts to advance the railway project, according to an analysis of the Port Sudan–Adré project. But Sudan is also well informed about the assets it has on its own, such as natural resources, geographical advantages, and its decades-old relationship with China, as the SWOT analysis shows; these assets are, however, constrained by governance weaknesses in the country, high debt levels, institutional fragmentation, and economic instability. Furthermore, armed conflict in Sudan broke out in April of 2023, negatively impacting the implementation environment by constraining institutional performance, reducing investors' confidence, and increasing sovereign risk ratings.

In conclusion, this study reveals that Sudan's participation in the Belt and Road Initiative will be successful if it is based not only on external investment opportunities but also on institutional self-sufficiency and the country's government dynamics. For effective participation, better coordination of policies, governance of infrastructure, sustainable financing options, and a long-term national planning framework should be put in place. The studies show that in the absence of meaningful institutional reforms and more certainty in the political process, Sudan may find it difficult to turn agreements on strategic cooperation into policy decisions.

The study also contributes to a broader discussion on China-Africa connections, infrastructure-based development, and the institutional features of infrastructure cooperation. It also further demonstrates the critical importance of institutional coordination and of embedding large-scale interventions into a wider socio-economic development plan for their success in politically and economically fragile states, such as Sudan.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, several policy recommendations can be proposed to strengthen Sudan's ability to benefit from cooperation under China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). These recommendations address the political, economic, institutional, and infrastructural challenges identified throughout the analysis and aim to support more effective and sustainable Sudan–China cooperation.

First, Sudan should strengthen institutional coordination mechanisms related to strategic infrastructure projects and BRI cooperation. The study demonstrates that weak coordination among government institutions has negatively affected the implementation of major projects, such as the Port Sudan–Adré railway. To address this issue, Sudan should establish a specialized national coordination mechanism or intergovernmental unit responsible for planning, negotiating, monitoring, and coordinating BRI-

related projects across relevant ministries and institutions. Such a mechanism could improve policy consistency, reduce administrative fragmentation, and enhance communication with international partners and financing institutions.

Second, improving governance and regulatory frameworks is essential for attracting sustainable infrastructure investment. Sudan should streamline legal and administrative procedures for infrastructure investment and strengthen transparency, accountability, and oversight mechanisms. Clear regulatory frameworks and stable investment policies would help improve investor confidence and reduce implementation delays associated with bureaucratic inefficiencies.

Third, Sudan should adopt more sustainable financing strategies for infrastructure development. Given the country's economic challenges and debt constraints, reliance on external borrowing alone may increase financial vulnerabilities. The government should therefore expand the use of public–private partnership (PPP) models, encourage foreign direct investment, and explore diversified financing arrangements involving regional and international development institutions. Strengthening debt management mechanisms and improving macroeconomic stability would also support a more favorable investment environment.

Fourth, infrastructure development priorities should focus on sectors with strong regional connectivity potential, particularly railway and maritime transport infrastructure. Sudan's strategic location along the Red Sea and its proximity to several landlocked African countries offer significant opportunities to develop regional trade corridors and logistics networks. Revitalizing railway infrastructure and improving port facilities could strengthen regional economic integration and enhance Sudan's role as a transport and transit hub within East and Central Africa.

Fifth, Sudan should strengthen its technical and institutional capacity for infrastructure planning and project implementation. This includes developing specialized expertise in project preparation, negotiation, financing, and infrastructure governance. Capacity-building programs and technical training for public institutions involved in infrastructure management would improve implementation effectiveness and long-term project sustainability.

Finally, political stability and security remain fundamental conditions for successful infrastructure cooperation and long-term investment. Continued political instability and armed conflict significantly undermine investor confidence and delay development projects. Efforts to restore political stability, strengthen state institutions, and improve security conditions are therefore essential to creating an environment conducive to sustainable infrastructure development and international cooperation.

Overall, the study suggests that Sudan's ability to benefit effectively from the Belt and Road Initiative depends not only on external financing opportunities but also on the

country’s internal institutional readiness, governance capacity, and long-term strategic planning. A coordinated and sustainable national approach to infrastructure development would improve Sudan’s ability to maximize the developmental opportunities associated with the Belt and Road Initiative while minimizing potential economic and institutional risks.

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